

Supplementary Material for: Comparison of modularity-based approaches for nodes clustering in hypergraphs

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A A symmetric hypergraph modularity

Chodrow et al. (2021) define a *symmetric* modularity, where for any partition \mathcal{C} of the set of nodes, the contribution of a hyperedge $e \in \mathcal{E}$ to the modularity of this partition is characterized only by the vector \mathbf{p} whose entries p_k count the number of nodes in e belonging to the k -th largest part in $e \cap \mathcal{C}$. More precisely, fix $\mathcal{C} = (C_1, \dots, C_K)$ a partition of V into K parts and consider $e \subset V$ a subset of nodes (here, e is not necessarily a hyperedge). Nodes in e are partitioned by \mathcal{C} into parts, namely $e \cap \mathcal{C} = (e_1, \dots, e_{J_e})$ for some $J_e \leq K$ (empty parts are discarded). Sorting these parts from largest to smallest, we obtain $e_{(1)}, \dots, e_{(J_e)}$ with $|e_{(1)}| \geq \dots \geq |e_{(J_e)}| \geq 1$. In other words, $e_{(k)}$ is the k -th largest non-empty part in $e \cap \mathcal{C}$. Then we let $p_k = |e_{(k)}|$ be the sizes of these size-ordered parts. The vector $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_{J_e})$ belongs to the set of partition vectors

$$\mathcal{P} = \{\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_J); p_1 \geq \dots \geq p_J \geq 1, \text{ for some } J \geq 1\}.$$

More generally, for any partition (e_1, \dots, e_J) of a subset of nodes $e \subset V$, we consider its ordering $(e_{(1)}, \dots, e_{(J)})$ in size-decreasing order, and let

$$\phi(e_1, \dots, e_J) = (|e_{(1)}|, \dots, |e_{(J)}|) \in \mathcal{P}.$$

Note that $\|\phi(e_1, \dots, e_J)\|_1 = \sum_k |e_{(k)}| = \sum_k |e_k| = |e|$ and we say that the partition vector $\phi(e_1, \dots, e_J)$ has size $|e|$. For any partition \mathcal{C} of the nodes, any subset of nodes $e \subset V$ and any partition vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}$, we say that e is *split* by \mathcal{C} into \mathbf{p} whenever $\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{p}$. In the following, the modularity of a partition \mathcal{C} will focus on how many hyperedges in H are split into different partition vectors $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}$.

In order to fully understand the links between all the modularities, we introduce a set of nodes subsets as follows. For any partition $\mathcal{C} = (C_1, \dots, C_K)$ of the set of nodes V and any partition vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}$, with $\|\mathbf{p}\|_0 = J \leq K$ and $\|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = s \leq n$, we let

$$C_{\mathbf{p}} = \{e = \{v_1, \dots, v_s\} \subset V; \phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{p}\},$$

the set of s -tuples of nodes that are split into the partition vector \mathbf{p} by the partition \mathcal{C} . With a slight abuse of notation, we can extend the definitions $e_H(\cdot)$ and $\text{Vol}_H(\cdot)$ to this set of nodes subsets (while those functions were originally defined on a unique subset of nodes). Thus we let

$$e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} w(e) 1\{e \in C_{\mathbf{p}}\} = \sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} w(e) 1\{\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{p}\},$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) &:= \sum_{e=\{v_1, \dots, v_s\} \subset V} 1\{\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{p}\} \times \prod_{i=1}^s \text{Vol}_H(\{v_i\} \cap \mathcal{C}) \\ &= \sum_{\substack{l_1, \dots, l_J \in \{1, \dots, K\} \\ l_j \text{ distinct}}} \prod_{j=1}^J \text{Vol}_H(C_{l_j})^{p_j}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that while the quantity $e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$ is obtained as a direct generalization of the function e_H defined on a unique subset of nodes, the quantity $\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$ is a bit more involved. It is a sum-product of volumes over all distinct clusters labels (l_1, \dots, l_J) that induce the same partition \mathbf{p} . These quantities are the generalizations of the former $\text{Vol}_H(C_k)^s$ that appeared when considering only size- s hyperedges with all nodes belonging to a unique cluster C_k .

Let us consider an example to better understand $\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$. We fix a partition \mathcal{C} of the nodes with $K \geq 3$ parts. Then, the only partition vectors of size $s = 2$ are $\mathbf{p} = (2)$ and $\mathbf{p} = (1, 1)$. Similarly, the only partition vectors of size $s = 3$ are $\mathbf{p} = (3); (2, 1); (1, 1, 1)$. Now the volumes $\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$ are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Vol}_H(C_{(2)}) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \text{Vol}_H(C_k)^2; & \text{Vol}_H(C_{(1,1)}) &= \sum_{k \neq l \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \text{Vol}_H(C_k) \text{Vol}_H(C_l); \\ \text{Vol}_H(C_{(3)}) &= \sum_{k=1}^K \text{Vol}_H(C_k)^3; & \text{Vol}_H(C_{(2,1)}) &= \sum_{k \neq l \in \{1, \dots, K\}} \text{Vol}_H(C_k)^2 \text{Vol}_H(C_l); \\ \text{Vol}_H(C_{(1,1,1)}) &= \sum_{\substack{k, l, m \in \{1, \dots, K\} \\ k, l, m \text{ distinct}}} \text{Vol}_H(C_k) \text{Vol}_H(C_l) \text{Vol}_H(C_m). \end{aligned}$$

Note that for any partition \mathcal{C} , any size s and any integer $c \in \{\lfloor s/2 \rfloor + 1, \dots, s\}$, we have the relation

$$\sum_{k=1}^K e_H^{s,c}(C_k) = \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}; \|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = s, p_1 = c} e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}).$$

In other words, the quantity $e_H^{s,c}(C_k)$ counts the number of hyperedges of size s having the majority of their nodes (c of them) in part C_k under partition \mathcal{C} . When summing this over all possible k , we get all possible splits of size- s hyperedges into partition vectors \mathbf{p} such that

the majority part has exactly c elements ($p_1 = c$).

Chodrow et al. (2021) also introduce a general affinity function $\Omega : \mathcal{P} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ that modulates the weight of the contribution of each partition vector \mathbf{p} . They define the symmetric modularity as:

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{\text{sym}}(H, \mathcal{C}) &= \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}} \left(\sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} w(e) 1\{\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}) = \mathbf{p}\} \log(\Omega(\mathbf{p})) - \text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) \Omega(\mathbf{p}) \right) \\ &= \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}} \left(e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) \log(\Omega(\mathbf{p})) - \text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) \Omega(\mathbf{p}) \right). \end{aligned}$$

A first term in this modularity counts how many (weighted) hyperedges are split by \mathcal{C} into the different partition vectors $\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}$, while a second term is related to the generalized volume $\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$. The extra weights $\log(\Omega(\mathbf{p}))$ and $\Omega(\mathbf{p})$ might not seem natural at first. In fact, they appear as the result of an approximate maximum likelihood approach in a specific degree-corrected hypergraph stochastic blockmodel (DCSHBM), in the same way as Newman (2016) did in a graph context. As a result, these extra weights $\log(\Omega(\mathbf{p}))$ and $\Omega(\mathbf{p})$ modulate the influence of the 2 terms whose differences are summed. Also, (up to the scaling factors $\log(\Omega(\mathbf{p}))$ and $\Omega(\mathbf{p})$), while the first term $e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$ in each sum still corresponds to an observed number of specific hyperedges, the second term $\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}})$ is not explicitly its expected value under some probabilistic null model. Nonetheless it is a correction term naturally arising from the consideration of a specific probabilistic model (the DCHSBM).

In practice, the affinity function Ω is estimated from an initial partition $\mathcal{C}^{\text{init}}$ through the (weighted) number of hyperedges split into each partition vector by $\mathcal{C}^{\text{init}}$, normalized by the volume of this partition vector under $\mathcal{C}^{\text{init}}$:

$$\forall \mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}, \quad \hat{\Omega}(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}} w(e) 1\{\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}^{\text{init}}) = \mathbf{p}\}}{\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{init}})} = \frac{e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{init}})}{\text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{init}})},$$

and the modularity becomes

$$\hat{Q}^{\text{sym}}(H, \mathcal{C}) = \sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}} \left(e_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) \log(\hat{\Omega}(\mathbf{p})) - \text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}) \hat{\Omega}(\mathbf{p}) \right). \quad (2)$$

The modularity \hat{Q}^{sym} represents a compromise between the 2 extremes $Q^{\text{w-clique}}$ and Q^{strict} , that goes beyond the one proposed by Q^{wsc} : all hyperedges play a role in this modularity, with weights depending on which partition vector \mathbf{p} they are split in by partition \mathcal{C} . This is at the cost of estimating many extra affinity parameter $\Omega(\mathbf{p})$.

Currently, the code provided by Chodrow et al. (2022) does not contain an implementation of an estimation of a general affinity function $\hat{\Omega}$. Indeed, such a general affinity function requires as many parameters as the total number of possible partitions of a size- s tuple of nodes for any $s \in \{2, \dots, S\}$ with $S = \max_{e \in \mathcal{E}} |e|$, which is huge. Note that their `demos` directory only contains in the file `parameterized-affinities.ipynb` an *experimental* version of a very specific parametrized affinity function.

B All-or-nothing modularity revisited

With the previous notation at stake, we may give a different presentation of Q^{aon} . The all-or-nothing affinity function Ω is defined by

$$\forall \mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P} \text{ such that } \|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = s, \quad \Omega^{\text{aon}}(\mathbf{p}) = \begin{cases} \omega_{s1} & \text{if } \|\mathbf{p}\|_0 = 1, \\ \omega_{s0} & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here, the ℓ_1 norm of an integer vector $\mathbf{p} = (p_1, \dots, p_J)$ is the sum of its entries $\|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = \sum_j p_j$ and its ℓ_0 norm is the number of its entries $\|\mathbf{p}\|_0 = J$. In other words, a partition vector \mathbf{p} has AON affinity

$$\Omega^{\text{aon}}(\mathbf{p}) = \sum_{s \geq 2} \left(\omega_{s1} \mathbf{1}\{\mathbf{p} = (s)\} + \omega_{s0} \mathbf{1}\{\|\mathbf{p}\|_0 \geq 2; \|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = s\} \right).$$

For each size s of a partition vector, this affinity function is parametrized by only two different values ω_{s1}, ω_{s0} . These parameters will modulate differently the contributions of hyperedges e depending on their size $s = |e|$ and on whether all their nodes belong to the same cluster (i.e., $\|\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C})\|_0 = 1$) or belong to at least 2 different clusters (i.e., $\|\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C})\|_0 \geq 2$). In particular, the volumes (1) computed for partition vectors \mathbf{p} such that $\|\mathbf{p}\|_0 = 1$ write

$$\text{Vol}_H(C_{(s)}) = \sum_{k=1}^K \text{Vol}_H(C_k)^s.$$

The AON affinity function will in practice be estimated from an initial partition $\mathcal{C}^{\text{init}}$ through

$$\forall s \geq 2, \quad \hat{\omega}_{s1} = \frac{e_H(C_{(s)}^{\text{init}})}{\sum_{k=1}^K \text{Vol}_H(C_k^{\text{init}})^s}; \quad \hat{\omega}_{s0} = \frac{\sum_{e \in \mathcal{E}_s} w(e) \mathbf{1}\{\|\phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}^{\text{init}})\|_0 \geq 2\}}{\sum_{\mathbf{p} \in \mathcal{P}; \|\mathbf{p}\|_0 \geq 2, \|\mathbf{p}\|_1 = s} \text{Vol}_H(C_{\mathbf{p}}^{\text{init}})}.$$

Finally, inserting that affinity function inside Q^{sym} and after some algebra, the resulting modularity becomes (up to additional constants that do not depend on \mathcal{C} and are thus neglected)

$$\begin{aligned} Q^{\text{aon}}(H, \mathcal{C}) &= - \sum_{s \geq 2} \hat{\beta}_s \left(\text{cut}_s(\mathcal{C}) + \hat{\gamma}_s \sum_{k=1}^K (\text{Vol}_H(C_k))^s \right) + c \\ &= \sum_{s \geq 2} \hat{\beta}_s \left(e_H(C_{(s)}) - \hat{\gamma}_s \sum_{k=1}^K (\text{Vol}_H(C_k))^s \right) + c \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{s \geq 2} \hat{\beta}_s \left(\sum_{C'_k \subset C_k; |C'_k|=s} e_H(C'_k) - \hat{\gamma}_s (\text{Vol}_H(C_k))^s \right) + c, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_s = \log \hat{\omega}_{s1} - \log \hat{\omega}_{s0}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_s = \hat{\beta}_s^{-1}(\hat{\omega}_{s1} - \hat{\omega}_{s0})$, the cut terms $\text{cut}_s(\mathcal{C})$ count the (weighted) number of hyperedges of size s that contain nodes in two or more distinct clusters; namely, $\text{cut}_s(\mathcal{C}) = |\mathcal{E}_s| - e_H(C_{(s)})$. The first line in Equation (4) is the expression of Q^{aon} given in Chodrow et al. (2021) while the following lines correspond to our rewriting, showing the similarities with the other previously defined modularities. While in general we may expect that $\hat{\omega}_{s1} > \hat{\omega}_{s0}$ so that both $\hat{\beta}_s, \hat{\gamma}_s > 0$, we then recover in this expression a sum of difference terms between a count of specific hyperedges (those entirely included in a cluster) and a correcting volume term.

C Linking parameters in HSBM and DCHSBM-like

If we consider a DCHSBM-like model generating multiset hypergraphs with equal cluster proportions, then we get using twice Baye’s rule,

$$\begin{aligned} p_s &= \frac{\mathbb{P}(e = \{v_1, \dots, v_s\} \in \mathcal{E}_s; \exists 1 \leq k \leq K, \phi(e \cap \mathcal{C}^{\text{true}}) \subset C_k^{\text{true}})}{|\mathcal{E}_s|/n^s} \\ &= \frac{\alpha_s K (K/n)^s}{|\mathcal{E}_s|/n^s} = \frac{\alpha_s K^{s+1}}{|\mathcal{E}_s|}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other way round, if we consider a HSBM generating simple hypergraphs with cluster proportions π_k , then we get using twice Baye’s rule,

$$\alpha_s = \frac{p_s [\alpha_s \sum_k \pi_k^s + \beta_s (1 - \sum_k \pi_k^s)]}{\sum_k \pi_k^s},$$

and in the particular case of equal cluster proportions, namely $\pi_k = 1/K$, then this leads to

$$\alpha_s = \frac{p_s \beta_s (K^{s-1} - 1)}{1 - p_s}.$$

D Values for ground truth modularity

Table 1 shows mean and standard deviations values of the modularities at the ground truth clustering for each method (each one focusing on a specific modularity definition, as summarized in Table 1 from the manuscript) and each scenario. We observe that the IRMM algorithm that maximizes $Q^{\text{w-clique}}$ has a ground truth modularity close to 0.

Table 1: Mean value (and standard deviation) of ground truth modularities $Q^{\text{true}} = Q(H, \mathcal{C}^{\text{true}})$ for the 25 hypergraphs generated under each method and scenario.

scenario / method	AON-HMLL	CNM	IRMM	LSR
ScenA-HSBM				
A1: $n = 50$	-1440.28(253.46)	0.31(0.04)	-0.01(0.02)	0.23(0.04)
A2: $n = 100$	-3281.04(321.45)	0.34(0.02)	-0.01(0.02)	0.27(0.02)
A3: $n = 150$	-5089.41(349.39)	0.35(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.27(0.02)
A4: $n = 200$	-7007.19(431.96)	0.36(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.28(0.02)
A5: $n = 500$	-19151.93(657.66)	0.36(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.28(0.01)
ScenA-DCHSBM				
A1: $n = 50$	-1507.05(140.8)	0.38(0.03)	-0.02(0.02)	0.3(0.03)
A2: $n = 100$	-3214.43(259.46)	0.37(0.02)	0(0.02)	0.29(0.02)
A3: $n = 150$	-5055.25(307.23)	0.37(0.02)	-0.01(0.01)	0.29(0.02)
A4: $n = 200$	-6819.27(297.63)	0.37(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.29(0.02)
A5: $n = 500$	-18619.63(568.68)	0.36(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.29(0.01)
A6: $n = 1000$	-39925.19(782.67)	0.36(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.29(0.01)

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

scenario / method	AON-HMLL	CNM	IRMM	LSR
ScenA-hABCD				
A1: $n = 50$	-177.69(39.81)	0.27(0.1)	-0.02(0.07)	0.24(0.09)
A2: $n = 100$	-439.39(58.81)	0.34(0.07)	-0.01(0.04)	0.3(0.06)
A3: $n = 150$	-727.05(63.2)	0.36(0.04)	-0.01(0.03)	0.31(0.03)
A4: $n = 200$	-1040.2(69.62)	0.38(0.04)	-0.01(0.03)	0.33(0.04)
A5: $n = 500$	-3453.7(312.77)	0.42(0.01)	0(0.02)	0.36(0.01)
A6: $n = 1000$	-8578.86(633.97)	0.44(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.37(0.01)
ScenB-DCHSBM				
B1: $n = 50$	-4476.24(286.51)	0.38(0.02)	-0.01(0.01)	0.3(0.02)
B2: $n = 100$	-9895.18(438.98)	0.37(0.01)	-0.01(0.01)	0.29(0.01)
B3: $n = 150$	-15436.71(407.27)	0.37(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.29(0.01)
B4: $n = 200$	-21146.49(497.66)	0.36(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.29(0.01)
B5: $n = 500$	-57396.92(1005.76)	0.37(0)	0(0)	0.29(0)
B6: $n = 1000$	-122253.16(1071.73)	0.36(0)	0(0)	0.29(0)
ScenC-HSBM				
C1: $n = 50$	-1692.96(341.87)	0.22(0.04)	-0.01(0.02)	0.16(0.04)
C2: $n = 100$	-3818.35(526.14)	0.23(0.03)	-0.01(0.01)	0.16(0.03)
C3: $n = 150$	-6006.44(720.38)	0.24(0.03)	0(0.01)	0.17(0.03)
C4: $n = 200$	-8411.32(678.46)	0.24(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.17(0.02)
C5: $n = 500$	-23301.14(1133.75)	0.24(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.17(0.02)
ScenD-DCHSBM				
D1: $n = 50$	-3268.27(172.98)	0.47(0.03)	-0.01(0.02)	0.28(0.02)
D2: $n = 100$	-7377.67(213.42)	0.45(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.27(0.01)
D3: $n = 150$	-11692.36(325.51)	0.45(0.02)	-0.01(0.01)	0.27(0.01)
D4: $n = 200$	-15946(274.87)	0.45(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.27(0.01)
D5: $n = 500$	-43675.15(431.82)	0.45(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.27(0.01)
D6: $n = 1000$	-92887.89(1079.8)	0.45(0.01)	0(0)	0.27(0.01)
ScenE-DCHSBM				
E1: $n = 50$	-1496.2(102.41)	0.41(0.03)	-0.01(0.02)	0.33(0.02)
E2: $n = 100$	-3210.91(190.09)	0.41(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.33(0.02)
E3: $n = 150$	-5117.84(249)	0.41(0.02)	-0.01(0.01)	0.32(0.02)
E4: $n = 200$	-6902.04(311.24)	0.4(0.02)	-0.01(0.01)	0.32(0.01)
E5: $n = 500$	-19069.69(632.72)	0.4(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.32(0.01)
E6: $n = 1000$	-40020.25(699.77)	0.4(0)	0(0)	0.32(0)
ScenF-DCHSBM				
F1: $n = 50$	-1401.74(122.37)	0.33(0.03)	-0.02(0.02)	0.26(0.02)
F2: $n = 100$	-3045.16(240.8)	0.32(0.02)	0(0.02)	0.25(0.02)
F3: $n = 150$	-4990.03(275.21)	0.32(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.25(0.01)
F4: $n = 200$	-6623.92(208.33)	0.33(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.26(0.02)
F5: $n = 500$	-18654.39(359.67)	0.32(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.25(0.01)
F6: $n = 1000$	-39341.82(941.03)	0.32(0.01)	0(0)	0.25(0.01)
ScenZ-hABCD				
Z1: $n = 100$	-529.92(164.11)	0.28(0.07)	-0.02(0.04)	0.26(0.08)
Z2: $n = 150$	-782.78(209.52)	0.33(0.05)	-0.02(0.04)	0.31(0.05)

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Table 1 – continued from previous page

scenario / method	AON-HMLL	CNM	IRMM	LSR
Z3: $n = 200$	-961.22(128.09)	0.35(0.04)	-0.01(0.02)	0.34(0.03)
Z4: $n = 500$	-2457.49(132.12)	0.39(0.02)	0(0.01)	0.41(0.02)
Z5: $n = 1000$	-5027.19(177.84)	0.41(0.01)	0(0.01)	0.43(0.01)

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